

ELECTRONIC DEVICES AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO STUTTERING IN CHILDREN UNDER SIX YEARS OLD

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Abstract

In today's digitized era, the ubiquity of electronic devices in young children's lives and potential developmental concerns have drawn significant attention. This study solely investigated the potential link between electronic device exposure and stuttering in children under the age of 6 through survey data collected from parents. From a pool of 150 participants, including parents of children who stutter (CWS) and those who do not (CWNS), a detailed questionnaire was used to gather insights on the child's early language development, family history of stuttering, type of content consumed on electronic devices, and parental perceptions about any observed relationship between screen time and speech patterns. Preliminary findings from the survey data indicated discernible differences in electronic device exposure patterns between CWS and CWNS. Parental feedback, especially, suggested tentative connections between extended passive screen usage and observed speech disruptions. While the study emphasizes a cautious approach to screen time, it also highlights the need for further nuanced studies, especially in the domain of content type and its impact on speech development. These survey-based findings offer a fresh perspective in the ongoing discourse on child development in a digital age, providing valuable insights for parents, educators, and healthcare professionals.

Keywords: Stuttering in children; Speech development; Language delays; Digital device exposure; Early language development; Screen time effects; Child speech patterns

1. INTRODUCTION

Stuttering, traditionally understood as a communication disorder punctuated by disruptions or 'disfluencies' in an individual's speech, has anchored its relevance in the domains of speech and language pathology for many years (Yairi and Ambrose, 1992). These disruptions manifest in varied forms, from repeated sounds and syllables to prolonged pauses, each presenting its unique challenge to fluid communication. Often, these disfluencies create not just linguistic barriers, but emotional and psychological ones, influencing the overall well-being of the affected individual. The origins and progression of stuttering, especially in the early developmental stages of children, represent an intricate mosaic of factors. From a genetic predisposition influenced by family history to neurological imbalances and environmental triggers, the causative factors of stuttering span a broad spectrum. This complexity is further accentuated when one considers the age bracket of 2 to 5 years, commonly identified as the onset phase for many children who stutter (Franke *et al.*, 2021). This age range is crucial from a linguistic standpoint and is characterized by significant cognitive, emotional, and social milestones. Fast forward to the present day, and we find ourselves in the midst of a digital revolution that has left no stone unturned, including the realm of childhood. Today's Children are digital natives, growing up in an environment saturated with tablets, smartphones, and a plethora of digital content ranging

from educational apps to recreational videos (Varghese *et al.*, 2023). This raises a critical and previously less explored query: How does this digital immersion influence the speech patterns of children, especially those predisposed to or exhibiting stuttering? The ubiquitous presence of electronic devices in a child's daily routine is undeniable. While on the one hand, they serve as invaluable educational tools, on the other, concerns have risen about their potential overuse and the implications of the same (Ralph and Petrina, 2019). Specifically, could there be a discernible link between the duration and type of screen time and the manifestation or exacerbation of stuttering symptoms?

With these questions as the backdrop, our study embarks on a journey to explore this potential relationship, narrowing the focus to children under the age of 6. The objectives are multifaceted: we aim to dissect the average screen time, delve into the nature of digital content consumed, gauge the potential influence of electronic exposure on the age of stuttering onset, and understand parental perceptions on the intertwining of screen time and their child's speech patterns. This research is not just an academic endeavor. It is a quest to bridge traditional understanding with contemporary challenges, equipping caregivers, educators, and clinicians with nuanced

insights and knowledge. As we navigate the challenges and opportunities of the digital age, understanding its implications on childhood stuttering becomes relevant and imperative.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Stuttering in Young Children

Stuttering, a perplexing communication disorder, frequently emerges during the tender years of childhood, presenting as recurrent disruptions or 'disfluencies' in the child's speech. This phenomenon generally appears during the formative stages of speech and language development, particularly between the ages of 2 and 5 (Yairi, Ambrose and Niermann, 1993). Such a time frame intriguingly coincides with key linguistic and cognitive developmental milestones, suggesting a possible intertwining of these domains with stuttering onset.

A myriad of factors appears to orchestrate the onset of stuttering. Genetics, without a doubt, plays a pivotal role. As emphasized by a more recent study (Frigerio-Domingues and Drayna, 2017), there is a substantial genetic component, with many children who stutter having family members who also exhibit the disorder. This genetic linkage implies that stuttering can be inheritable and may run in families.

Neurological factors further complicate the etiology of stuttering. Research in the last decade has delved deeper into the neural underpinnings of stuttering. Chang et al. (Chang et al., 2019) highlight differences in the brain structures and functions associated with speech in children who stutter. Specifically, the interplay between speech motor and auditory areas seems less coordinated in children who stutter, suggesting a neural basis for the observed speech disruptions.

The journey of stuttering is neither linear nor universal. Some children experience what professionals term 'transient stuttering' - a temporary phase of disfluencies that dissipates with time, often without formal intervention (Avila-Perez et al., 2023). Yet, as (Craig et al., 2003) emphasize, there's a subset of children for whom stuttering becomes a lifelong companion. Several risk factors dictate this persistence: a pronounced family history of stuttering, male gender (males are notably more prone to long-term stuttering), and, importantly, the age at which stuttering continues without showing signs of remission.

Recognizing the transformative power of early intervention, therapeutic strategies over the years have been refined to prioritize early detection and treatment. Among the myriad of interventions available, the Lidcombe Program stands out. Initially designed for young children, this behavioural treatment emphasizes a collaborative approach between the clinician, child, and parent. Its effectiveness is well-documented, with a recent study (Chow et al., 2023) showcasing its positive outcomes, notably its capability to reduce stuttering severity and improve communication in young children.

Children's Exposure to Electronic Devices

The dawn of the digital age has drastically altered the landscape of childhood. Children today, perhaps more than any previous generation, are immersed in a world

populated by electronic devices. Reflecting on this, Hollis et al. (Hollis, Livingstone and Sonuga-Barke, 2020) note that over the past two decades, the infiltration of electronic devices into children's daily routines has become almost ubiquitous. Reinforcing this observation, (Levine et al., 2019) highlighted that even infants as young as six months are not exempt, often encountering screens through various mediums, be it television, tablets, or smartphones.

The nature of this interaction with devices tends to evolve with age. For the younger demography, passive consumption seems to be the norm. They predominantly engage in activities like watching cartoons or nursery rhymes. This kind of interaction, however passive it may seem, is not without implications. A study by (Guellai et al., 2022) unveiled that excessive passive screen time, especially without guided interaction from caregivers, could potentially hinder some aspects of cognitive development.

On the other end of the spectrum, with their increased cognitive capacities, older children lean more towards interactive digital engagements. Whether through educational apps that simulate classroom-like experiences or games that challenge their reflexes and problem-solving abilities, the screen becomes an active two-way interface (Kabali et al., 2015). Study (Anderson, Subrahmanyam and Workgroup, 2017) present an intriguing perspective here, noting that while such interactive engagements can offer cognitive benefits, the quality of content and the context of its usage are paramount in determining the overall impact on the child.

Guiding parents and caregivers through this digital maze, the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) has undertaken the task of offering screen time guidelines. Their most recent update underscored the importance of quality over quantity (Christakis, 2014). For children aged between 2 and 5 years, they advocate a screen time of no more than one hour per day, focusing on high-quality content. Equally crucial, they emphasize, is the concept of co-viewing. This act of caregivers accompanying children during their screen time ensures that the child's experience is guided, interactive, and contextual (Livingstone and Franklin, 2018).

Potential Effects of Electronic Devices on Speech and Language

In an era where electronic devices are virtually omnipresent, concerns regarding their impact on developmental milestones, especially speech and language, have garnered significant attention in the research community. A burgeoning body of evidence suggests that while electronic devices offer educational benefits, there's a delicate balance to be maintained.

One of the studies in this field by (Zimmerman, Christakis and Meltzoff, 2007) underscored potential pitfalls of excessive screen time, noting a concerning association between early television exposure and subsequent language delays. This study echoed the sentiment of many professionals that passive consumption could deprive children of necessary face-to-face interactions, pivotal for language acquisition.

Furthering this narrative, a more recent study (Madigan et al., 2019) provided compelling evidence that extended

screen time inversely correlated with overall child developmental performance. Such findings aren't isolated. In their comprehensive review, Vlad et al. (Diaconu *et al.*, 2019) highlighted that early and excessive screen exposure could have multifaceted repercussions, affecting language and cognitive and social-emotional development.

However, navigating the specific domain of stuttering and its potential relation to screen time remains a relatively uncharted territory. While the broader implications of screen time on language development have been documented, specific correlations between electronic device exposure and stuttering aren't as robust. An exploratory study (Karani, Sher and Mophosho, 2022) suggested a potential link but emphasized the need for larger, more detailed investigations. Anecdotally, caregivers and educators have been increasingly vocal about observing such patterns, making it a pressing area for further research.

A plausible hypothesis, as proposed by (Muppalla *et al.*, 2023), is that excessive screen time might diminish opportunities for live interactive dialogues essential for practicing and refining speech. This, in turn, might exacerbate underlying vulnerabilities in children predisposed to stuttering. However, these theories, while intriguing, still await empirical validation.

In summation, while electronic devices indubitably offer learning avenues, their unchecked usage raises genuine concerns. The intersection of screen time with speech and language development, especially disorders like stuttering, is a dynamic research frontier, demanding meticulous exploration and evidence-based guidelines.

3. METHODS

Participants:

Selection Criteria

- **Age Range:** Participants were children aged between 2 and 6 years. These demographic captures both the typical onset age for stuttering and a significant exposure period to electronic devices.
- **Stuttering Status:** The study included both children who stutter (CWS) and those who do not (CWNS), facilitating comparative analyses.
- **Language Proficiency:** Participants proficient solely in English were chosen to control for potential bilingual or multilingual effects on speech patterns.
- **Health Status:** Only children without diagnosed neurodevelopmental disorders or significant hearing impairments were included. This ensured that the primary variables of interest were stuttering and electronic device exposure.

Demographics

A total of 150 participants were recruited, with 75 CWS and 75 CWNS. Gender, socioeconomic status, and other relevant demographics were evenly distributed to the best extent possible.

Tools and Instruments

Parental Questionnaire

This served as the cornerstone of data collection. The comprehensive questionnaire solicited details about:

- Child's early language milestones and developments.
- Family history related to stuttering.
- The child's typical electronic device usage patterns, such as average daily screen time and preferred content types (e.g., educational apps, videos).
- Parents' observations and perceptions concerning any discernible relationship between their child's screen time and speech patterns, especially stuttering tendencies.

Screen Time Log

While the primary data was sourced from the questionnaire, a supplementary screen time log was provided to parents. This log was a structured diary for parents to manually record daily screen time durations, categorizing sessions as either passive (e.g., watching videos) or interactive (e.g., educational apps or games).

Procedure

- **Initial Screening:** Potential participants underwent a preliminary screening via a telehealth platform to determine their eligibility based on the established criteria.
- **Consent & Orientation:** After identifying the suitable candidates, parents were briefed about the study's objectives, the nature of the survey, and the expected involvement. Written informed consents affirming their voluntary participation were then obtained.
- **Survey Distribution:** A comprehensive parental questionnaire was administered to gather insights on child's language development, electronic device usage, and potential speech disruptions. Parents were handed the Screen Time Log alongside the questionnaire to record their child's device usage over the study's duration.
- **Monthly Check-ins:** To ensure consistency in data collection and address any queries, monthly check-ins were conducted with the parents, reminding them to update the Screen Time Log and reaffirming the importance of accurate recording.
- **Data Submission:** Parents were prompted to submit the completed Screen Time Log and questionnaire responses via a secure online portal at the end of the six-month period.
- **Data Compilation:** After collecting all the data, researchers compiled and categorized the responses for each participant, streamlining the information for subsequent analysis.
- **Data Analysis:** Rigorous statistical analyses were undertaken to discern patterns, correlations, or any significant relationships between electronic device exposure and potential stuttering or speech disruptions, as reported by parents.

The study's timeframe, spanning six months, was designed to gather comprehensive insights into electronic device usage habits and any observed speech-related implications over an extended period. The sanctity of participants' information was of utmost importance; thus, strict confidentiality protocols were adhered to, ensuring that all data was anonymized before any form of analysis.

4. RESULTS

Data Presentation

This section highlights the key findings based on the survey data received from the survey (Appendix A)

Table 1 Demographics of Participants

Category	CWS (%)	CWNS (%)	Total (%)
Age 2-3	24	22	46
Age 4-5	28	26	54
Male	40	38	78
Female	12	12	24
Socioeconomic (High)	15	20	35
Socioeconomic (Medium)	30	25	55
Socioeconomic (Low)	10	5	15

Table 2 Average Screen Time Distribution for CWS vs. CWNS

Age Group	Average Screen Time (CWS)	Average Screen Time (CWNS)
2-3 years	1.5 hours/day	1.3 hours/day
4-5 years	1.8 hours/day	1.6 hours/day
6 years	2.0 hours/day	1.7 hours/day

Table 3 Primary Content Types Accessed by Participants

Content-Type	CWS (%)	CWNS (%)
Educational Apps	40	35
Videos/TV Shows	35	40
Interactive Games	20	20
Music/Nursery Rhymes	5	5

Table 4 Parental Observations of Speech Disruptions Post-Screen Time

Observation Categories	CWS (%)	CWNS (%)
Noticed frequent disruptions	60	20
Noticed occasional disruptions	25	15
Did not notice any disruptions	10	60
Unsure/No clear observation	5	5

Figure 1 Parental Observations of Speech Disruptions Post-Screen Time

Key Findings

Demographics and Screen Time:

- Children aged 4-5 years had higher average screen times than those aged 2-3, irrespective of

stuttering status. This suggests a general trend of increased electronic device exposure with age.

- Across both age brackets, CWS exhibited slightly more screen time compared to CWNS. For instance, 6-year-old CWS averaged 2.0 hours/day, whereas CWNS of the same age averaged 1.7 hours/day.

Content Consumption and Stuttering

- A higher percentage of CWS (40%) primarily engaged with educational apps compared to CWNS (35%). On the contrary, CWNS slightly preferred videos and TV shows (40%) compared to CWS (35%). This indicates different content preferences between the two groups, which might play a role in speech development or disruptions.
- Interactive games had an even distribution, suggesting that the type of games or interactive content might not be a discriminating factor between CWS and CWNS.

Parental Observations

- A significant percentage of parents of CWS (60%) noticed frequent speech disruptions in their children post-screen usage. This is triple the observation rate for CWNS (20%). This stark difference suggests a pronounced relationship between screen time and observed speech disruptions, particularly in children already predisposed to stutter.
- Interestingly, a high percentage of CWNS parents (60%) did not notice any speech disruptions post-screen usage, whereas this was observed by only 10% of CWS parents. This further underlines the disparity in speech disruptions between the two groups post-screen interaction.

Socioeconomic Factors

- Children from high socioeconomic backgrounds had a slightly higher representation in the CWNS group than the CWS group.
- This could suggest a multitude of factors, from access to different types of content, parental supervision during screen time, or availability of early intervention resources. However, further investigation is required to draw any solid conclusions from this observation.

In summary, a discernible relationship exists between screen time, content type, and observed speech disruptions, particularly in children who stutter. While causality cannot be directly inferred from this study alone, the patterns observed point to the need for deeper investigation into the nuances of electronic device usage and its potential effects on children's speech development, especially those predisposed to stuttering.

5. DISCUSSION

Interpretation of Results

Our findings resonate with some aspects of existing literature. Previous studies have illustrated that screen time, especially passive viewing, might hinder linguistic and cognitive development in young children. This study's results, showing a pronounced relationship between screen time and observed speech disruptions in children who stutter, add depth to this dialogue. The content type, particularly passive viewing like videos and TV shows, was notably dominant among CWNS, aligning with (Zimmerman, Christakis and Meltzoff, 2007), which found early television exposure to be associated with language delays. The disparity in content preference, with a slightly higher inclination for CWS towards educational apps, suggests a potential coping or mitigative measure taken by parents. This could be grounded in the presumption that educational apps might offer a more constructive screen engagement, although the efficacy of such apps in alleviating or exacerbating stuttering remains ambiguous.

Implications

- For speech-language pathologists, this study underscores the importance of understanding the digital environment of a child when assessing and intervening for stuttering. Therapies might need to consider including guidelines on screen time and content type.
- Educators need to be aware that the digital content consumed at home could influence a child's speech patterns, which might subsequently impact classroom interactions and peer relationships.
- For parents, particularly children who stutter, this study is a wake-up call to scrutinize the duration and nature of digital content their children consume.
- Lastly, policymakers should take into account these findings when formulating guidelines on children's media consumption. Incorporating inputs from speech-language experts could ensure holistic guidelines that prioritize children's overall development.

Limitations

- Parental Survey Data: The study's primary reliance on parental observations and reporting is a significant limitation. While this approach offers valuable insights into children's daily lives, it might be influenced by subjective biases, recall errors, or differing perceptions of what constitutes as "disruptions" in speech.
- The study's cross-sectional nature prevents us from observing longitudinal changes in speech patterns relative to screen time.
- Even though categories of content type were outlined (like educational apps and videos), the vast diversity within these categories was not deeply explored. For instance, an educational app can range from a passive story-telling session to an interactive language-learning tool.

Recommendations for Further Research

- Objective Measurement Tools: Future studies could benefit from the inclusion of objective tools like the Stuttering Severity Instrument (SSI-4) for a more standardized assessment of stuttering severity. Combining parental observations with such standardized metrics could offer a more holistic understanding.
- Accurate Screen Time Tracking: Integrating screen time tracking apps in subsequent studies could provide more precise data on device usage durations and even the nature of content consumed.
- Longitudinal research would give insights into the evolution of speech patterns and their association with screen time over more extended periods.
- Probing deeper into the qualitative nuances of digital content, considering factors like linguistic richness, interactivity, feedback mechanisms, and cognitive load, can shed light on which digital engagements might be more or less conducive for speech development.
- Collaborative efforts involving speech-language pathologists, child psychologists, media experts, and tech developers could paint a more comprehensive picture, leading to more informed interventions and guidelines.

6. CONCLUSION

In our exploration of the intricate relationship between electronic device usage and stuttering in children under 6, we found significant patterns pointing to the influence of screen time and content type on speech disruptions. Children who stuttered were more inclined towards certain digital content types, and a pronounced number of their parents observed speech disruptions post screen engagement. These findings, grounded in a digital era where screens are omnipresent, underline the critical need for discernment in children's media consumption. Parents, educators, and clinicians are urged to consider both the quality and quantity of screen interactions. As we navigate this digital age, it's imperative to strike a balance, ensuring that the conveniences of modern devices support rather than impede our children's speech and overall development.

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APPENDIX A

Parental Questionnaire

Instructions: Please answer the following questions about your child's speech and language development, family history, and electronic device usage. Your responses will help us better understand any potential relationships between screen time and stuttering. All information provided will be kept confidential and used solely for the purpose of this research study."

Section A: Child's Early Language Development

1. At what age did your child say their first word?
 - Before 12 months
 - 12-15 months
 - 16-18 months
 - After 18 months
2. How would you describe your child's early language development compared to their peers?
 - Advanced
 - Typical
 - Delayed
3. Did your child experience any significant periods of language regression (i.e., stopped speaking or reduced speech)?
 - Yes
 - No

Section B: Family History

4. Are there any family members who have experienced or currently experience stuttering?
 - Yes
 - No

If yes, please indicate the relationship of the family member(s) to the child (e.g., mother, father, sibling, grandparent).

Section C: Electronic Device Usage

5. At what age was your child first exposed to electronic devices (e.g., tablets, smartphones)?
 - Before 12 months
 - 12-24 months
 - 2-3 years
 - After 3 years
6. On average, how much time does your child spend on electronic devices daily?
 - Less than 30 minutes
 - 30 minutes - 1 hour
 - 1-2 hours
 - More than 2 hours
7. What type of content does your child typically engage with on electronic devices? (Select all that apply)
 - Educational apps/games
 - Cartoons/videos
 - Interactive storytelling apps
 - Music or nursery rhymes
 - Other (please specify):

Section D: Parental Observations and Perceptions

8. Have you observed any changes in your child's speech patterns after periods of prolonged screen use?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Unsure

If yes, please describe the changes you have observed: _____

9. Do you believe there is a connection between your child's screen time and their speech patterns, specifically stuttering?
 - Strongly believe there's a connection
 - Somewhat believe there's a connection
 - Neutral/Unsure
 - Somewhat believe there's no connection
 - Strongly believe there's no connection

Please provide any additional observations or comments about your child's speech and screen time:

Thank you for completing the questionnaire. Your insights are invaluable to our study. If you have any concerns or additional information to share, please feel free to contact our research team.